

Assessment of Compact Minkowski Fractal Microstrip Filter for Band Applications

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Abstract

A rapid growth in advanced wireless communication applications demands compact and reconfigurable microstrip filter structures. However, meeting these requirements comes with many challenges, namely increased design complexity, system size, its fabrication and cost effectiveness. Accordingly, paper aims to design a reconfigurable microstrip filter in terms of their geometrical structures and operational performances. A Reconfigured Compact Minkowski Fractal Microstrip Filter with inverted C shape and first iteration is proposed. The proposed work discuss about the design flow, parameters associated with it and simulation results of a compact Minkowski fractal microstrip band pass filter for different dielectric constant and thickness. Minkowski fractal Structured filter with substrate thickness of 0.8mm is operating at 5.1GHz with bandwidth of 1.6 GHz for 9.9 dielectric. And the same filter has a bandwidth of 2.4 GHz for 4.4 dielectric. A dual bandwidth is also achieved in the proposed filter with each of 0.8GHz bandwidth that can be used for different applications. A single filter can be used for more than one application. Minkowski Fractal Microstrip Filter is compact with good bandwidth and dedicated to C and X band applications.

Keywords: Simulations, Filter, X and C band, geometrical structures, applications

I. Introduction

Most of the Microstrip filters are more popular and have more scope because of its miniature size, cost effectiveness, less weight and easy to fabricate. Hence these filters have found many applications in RF transceivers and wireless communications. Microstrip filters have less insertion loss, small size, wide band with high selectivity, these parameters are very much required and important in design of modern wireless communication systems [1, 2]. Microwave circuit designers will always meet the most challenging targets like, to produce miniaturized components with multiband operations. To achieve these expectations, many fractal structures of different geometries are emerging and are becoming more attractive. Advantages of using these different geometries are compact size, part less electronic parts, and improved performance [3]. The applications of different geometries of fractals are to produce miniature -sized filters and the use of fractals have many advantages [2, 3, 4]. Apart from, researchers had successively proposed many types of fractals to reshape the original microstrip lines and to obtain small size of bandpass filters for wireless communication applications.

In modern wireless communication system applications, the wide band and narrowband microstrip bandpass filters plays a primitive role of sending the signal from transmitter and receiver. To achieve best performance of filter, it should be compact and easy to fabricate. Filters are two-port network used to control the frequency response. The most widely used filter in microwave applications is microstrip bandpass filters. The main aim of the bandpass filter is used to pass the signals in the desired range of frequencies [5].

Fractals are defined either as random or deterministic. There are several geometries in fractal like Hilbert, Minkowski, Peano, Koch, Sierpinski etc., which are used widely in most of the microwave & RF applications and in the design of compact fractal geometry filters [6]. These geometry filter provides better performance and compact size when compared to the non-fractalized filters. The resonant frequency will move towards the lowest frequency when the number of iteration increases [7].

Many basic fractal geometries fascinates the designers of microwave circuit for mass production of compact microstrip bandpass filters [8]. Microstrip with fractal-shaped resonators and its modified structures are used in conventional resonators to fabricate miniaturized bandpass filters with efficient performance and implementations [9]. Therefore researchers are attempting to make an effort on modifying versions of classical fractals to get more compact resonating structures. The reconfigured variants of Minkowski geometry fractal had proved its strength to propose microstrip bandpass filters with more compactness [10]. With spectacular results, Minkowski fractal bandpass filters are specified with good performance and reduced in size and harmonics [11]. More Magnifying characteristics of filters had made it to be more attractive and a growing latest research technologies had made this topic to be more focused and have lot of scope. Hence most of the research studies are dedicated to the design of compact microstrip filters. So it's worth to conclude that the application of various fractal geometries and their variants are used to reshape the filters, had revealed to be very successful to offer more size reduction besides the enhanced filter execution.

III. Mathematical Design and its Analysis

Insertion loss method with distributive circuit elements are used to design filter at microwave frequencies. Fifth order Butterworth microstrip filter is designed using dielectric constant 9.9 and 4.4. The classical steps followed to design a proposed filter as follows. The 5th order low pass filter is designed using the low pass prototype element values as per the maximally flat Butterworth table available in [1, 2, 3] almost in all most all microwave books. The prototype low pass filter is modified into bandpass filter followed by impedance and frequency scaling to construct the equivalent parallel coupled microstrip line layout. Then a fractal geometry of modified Minkowski is applied for further reduction of size of the filter.

The fractal geometry used for proposed filter is modified Minkowski curve and its generation method as shown in Fig 1. I.e each vertical microstrip line is one third of the original length and each horizontal microstrip line is $\frac{\omega n}{3}$ of the original length, such as

$0 \leq \omega n \leq n$ called as indentation factor.

The fractal geometry of Minkowski is derived using classical Minkowski curve is given as:

Each vertical microstrip line = $1/3^{\text{rd}}$ of the original length (1)

Each horizontal microstrip line = $Wn/3$ of the original length (2)

$0 \leq Wn \leq n$ Iteration factor (3)

The Minkowski fractal geometry is obtained by iteration method for n approaching to infinity and indentation values for n iterations are obtained as follows:

$$I_n = \frac{L}{3^n} (W_n) \quad (4)$$

L length of initial microstrip line, W_n indentation factor, n iteration order, $W=0.125\text{mm}$.

The modified Minkowski fractal structure generation method is shown in the Fig.1, for zero iteration the microstrip line will be straight line, first iteration the straight line will be bent into first curve of length $L/3$ and iteration length I_1 these values are shown in the equations (5) to (12)

Figure 1:

Generation of Minkowski fractal geometry

The bent geometries goes on increasing as the iterations increases as shown in the Fig. 1. Each parallel coupled microstrip lines of inverted C filter [1, 2, 3] can be reconfigured into modified Minkowski curve geometry by using iteration process. By using Esq. (1) to (4). The designed values of I, L for first iteration as follows:

For First Microstrip line $L_1 = 2.489\text{mm}$ $\therefore \frac{L_1}{3} = 0.829\text{mm}$, $W = 0.125\text{mm}$

$$\text{Using Eq. (4)} I_{1,1} = \frac{2.489}{3} (0.125\text{mm}) = 0.104\text{mm} \quad (5)$$

For $L_2 = 3.124\text{mm}$ $\therefore \frac{L_2}{3} = 1.041\text{mm}$, $W = 0.125\text{mm}$

$$I_{1,2} = \frac{3.124}{3} (0.125\text{mm}) = 0.130\text{mm} \quad (6)$$

For $L_3 = 2.997\text{mm}$ $\therefore \frac{L_3}{3} = 0.999\text{mm}$, $W = 0.125\text{mm}$

$$I_{1,3} = \frac{2.997}{3} (0.125\text{mm}) = 0.125\text{mm} \quad (7)$$

For $L_4 = 2.997\text{mm}$ $\therefore \frac{L_4}{3} = 0.999\text{mm}$, $W = 0.125\text{mm}$

$$I_{1,4} = \frac{2.997}{3} (0.125\text{mm}) = 0.125\text{mm} \quad (8)$$

$$I_{1,3} = I_{1,4} \quad (9)$$

For $L_5 = 3.124\text{mm}$ $\therefore \frac{L_5}{3} = 1.041\text{mm}$, $W = 0.125\text{mm}$

$$I_{1,5} = \frac{3.124}{3} (0.125\text{mm}) = 0.130\text{mm} \quad (10)$$

$$I_{1,2} = I_{1,5} \quad (11)$$

For $L_6 = 2.870\text{mm}$ $\therefore \frac{L_6}{3} = 0.957\text{mm}$, $W = 0.125\text{mm}$

$$I_{1,6} = \frac{2.870}{3} (0.125\text{mm}) = 0.119\text{mm} \quad (12)$$

Length of Microstrip Lines ($\frac{L_{1,n}}{3}$) in mm	Indentation Values($I_{1,n}$) in mm
0.829	0.104
1.041	0.130
0.999	0.125
0.999	0.125
1.041	0.130
0.957	0.119

Table 1: Length of Microstrip line and Indentation values for first Iteration

After the calculations of all the microstrip lines and indentation values from Eqs. (5) to (12) in mm is tabulated in table 1, now with the help of table 1 construction of modified Minkowski inverted C curve is using ADS tool. Such as a Reconfigured Minkowski inverted C curve structure- Iteration 1 with three divisions of $L/3$, such as $L=L/3$ is constructed as shown in the Fig 2. The same procedure is repeated for all other remaining five microstrip lines labelled as Microstrip Line (ML) from ML_1 to ML_6 for all microstrip lines in the filter. In between all the MLs the Connecting Lines (CL) are used to connect of all microstrip lines according to the order of the filter.

Figure 2: Reconfigured Minkowski inverted C curve structured filter

There are two ports port 1 and port 2 represented as P_1 and P_2 for input and output lets, acts bidirectional. The scattering parameters shown in the simulation results depends on these ports.

IV. Results and Discussions of Fractal Structured Microstrip Filter

For the Reconfigured Minkowski inverted C curve structure- Iteration 1, the dielectric constant and the substrate thickness is varied such as dielectric constants 9.9 and 4.4 keeping the substrate thickness constant of value 0.8mm.

Figure 3: simulation results for dielectric constant 9.9 and thickness 0.8mm

And focused more on dielectric constant 4.4 because for this a cost effective substrate flame retardant 4 (FR4) is used, hence for this material the substrate is varied and a dual band is observed and all these simulation results are discussed in Figs 3,4,5. In Fig 3, bandwidth is 1.6 GHz in S11 and S22 the scattering parameters for P1 and P2 respectively at -10dB. Insertion loss in between the

two ports P1 and P2 is -0.4dB from S12 (P1 to P2) and S21 (P2 to P1) with centre frequency 5.1GHz. For dielectric constant 9.9 and substrate thickness 0.8mm.

Figure 4: Simulation results for dielectric constant 4.4 and thickness 0.8mm

The bandwidth is 2.4 GHz for insertion loss of -0.6dB from S12 and S21 with centre frequency 7.65 GHz. for 4.4 dielectric constant and 0.8mm of substrate thickness as shown in Fig 4. As the constant of dielectric decreases, resonating frequency shifts to the higher values as shown in the Fig 4. This substrate is cost effective hence more focused on this and further discussed in Fig 5.

Figure 5: Simulation results for Dielectric Constant 4.4 and Thickness 1.6mm

By varying the thickness of the substrate to 1.6mm the filter will act like a dual band operated filter as shown in Fig 5, resonating at two different frequencies of 4GHz and 8GHz. With bandwidth of 0.8GHz at -10dB, return loss of greater than 20dB over S11 and S22. Loss of Insertion is -2dB over S12 and S21. Conclusions from all Figs: 2 to 4 are tabulated in the Table 2.

Filter Type	Size of the Filter(cm ²)	Bandwidth	
		Dielectric Constant 4.4	Dielectric Constant 9.9
Non- Fractal Microstrip Filter [1,2,3]	1.524X 1.1685	1.7GHz at -1dB	1.56GHz at -0.7dB
Proposed Filter:Minkowski Fractal Microstrip Filter	0.8082 X 0.794	2.4 GHz at -3dB	1.6GHz at -0.6dB

Table 2: Comparative study

From the comparative study table 2, the proposed filter - Minkowski fractal microstrip filter is more compact with good bandwidth. As the dielectric constant decreases the bandwidth increases. FR4 is used for cost effectiveness, performance is very good and effective.

A unified research team at Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy is working on different issues of e-governance and smart cities. Emergency number as cases, in the mean while students are found to focus on different issues one of them is band issue and smart cities are continuous[12,13, 14]

IV. Conclusion

The proposed Minkowski fractal structured filter is more compact with good bandwidth and less insertion loss than the non-fractal microstrip filter with 50% reduction in size. A compact filter is designed for dielectric constant 9.9 and a cost effective substrate flame retardant 4 of 4.4 dielectric constant. A dual band is also achieved that can be used for different applications i.e. a single filter can be used for different applications. Filter is compact with good bandwidth and dedicated to C and X band applications. The limitations of this fractal structure are not cost effective for dielectric constant 9.9, band width decreases when the order of iteration approaching higher values because a coupling becomes weaker between the fractal perturbed coupled lines compare to no fractal coupled lines, hence not much focused of higher iteration values.

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